

A novel network for detecting long continuing currents in the metropolitan area of Belo Horizonte

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Abstract — This paper describes the first experimental results of a new lightning detection network installed in the metropolitan area of Belo Horizonte, Brazil, with the specific purpose of evaluating the occurrence of lightning continuing currents, which are currently not detected by conventional Lightning Location Systems. It is known that these current components are responsible for causing severe thermal damage in power systems, as well as the ignition of large-scale wildfires. The distinctive aspect of this network is the type of sensor deployed - it features two channels whose technical specifications allow the recording of physical processes within a wide frequency range. Throughout the text, typical waveform examples of lightning electric fields are presented. Additionally, a preliminary statistical study regarding the average duration of these continuing currents is reported, and a brief discussion is provided.

Keywords — lightning, lightning flash, return stroke, continuing current, electric field, lightning location system.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lightning is a natural phenomenon responsible for a significant number of fatalities in living beings, unscheduled failures and outages in power systems, physical damage to buildings and structures, and extensive wildfires, among other deleterious effects [1,2]. The initiation of lightning flashes within thunderclouds results from the interaction of the strong local electric field with specific secondary processes, such as the incidence of cosmic rays from outer space, according to some researchers [3,4]. The primary outcome of this interaction is the formation of an ionized region, within which a highly conductive plasma leader is materialized and can propagate

over tens to hundreds of kilometers, both horizontally and vertically [5].

Depending on the region of development of this leader, lightning flashes can be categorized as either cloud or cloud-to-ground (CG) discharges [6]. From the perspective of the associated deleterious effects, cloud flashes are particularly relevant for the performance of satellites and aircraft, given their potential to cause electromagnetic interference in these systems. On the other hand, CG lightning poses damaging effects on various essential terrestrial systems, which is why the vast majority of studies associated with lightning protection concentrate efforts on evaluating the effects produced by this specific type of discharge [2].

When a plasma channel originating from a thundercloud connects to the ground potential, a very intense transient electromagnetic process begins, known as the return stroke (RS) [3]. This involves the flow of an impulsive electric current to the ground, which reaches tens to hundreds of kiloamperes in a few microseconds and returns to zero after a few hundred microseconds [7].

The impulsive phase of the RS current rarely lasts more than 1 millisecond. However, in some cases, after this stage, the lightning channel remains active, emitting persistent luminosity. This observation is associated with the flow of another current component through the plasma channel, known as the lightning continuing current (CC) [6]. The continuing current has lower amplitudes, in the order of a few hundred amperes, but can flow for very long intervals, up to hundreds of milliseconds. This

current, by transferring a significant amount of charge to the ground and by keeping the hot plasma channel connected to the point of incidence for extended periods, has a high potential to cause thermal damage, especially in the adjacent region [4,6,8].

The statistical characterization of the continuing current's intensity, duration, charge transfer and frequency of occurrence is a critical need for both scientific research and industry applications [7]. Moreover, there is a consensus among researchers and experts that thermal damage from the continuing current can lead to various deleterious effects on society, although this type of assessment has not yet been systematically carried out under real-world conditions. Specifically, the continuing current has the potential to cause:

- i. Physical damage to buildings and structures [9,10].
- ii. Rupture of cables and conductors in transmission lines and power distribution networks [11,12].
- iii. Permanent damage to wind turbine generators [13,14].

Furthermore, the lightning CC is also linked to a concerning global issue - the occurrence of large-scale wildfires, such as those observed annually in regions like Australia, the United States, Canada, and parts of Western Europe. These fires not only result in massive carbon emissions, often exceeding the annual output of major economies, but they also endanger human life, destroy property, and cause lasting damage to local flora and fauna [15–17]. Research on the occurrence of this type of fire in Brazil lacks much experimental data, and there is a growing demand for this type of investigation, especially in the cerrado and pantanal biomes [18–22].

Continuing currents are usually categorized into three groups, according to their duration: (a) very short continuing currents (VSCC), which last from 1 to 10 milliseconds; (b) short continuing currents (SCC), which last between 10 and 40 milliseconds; and (c) long continuing currents, which remain active for more than 40 milliseconds (LCC) [23–26]. The longer the CC, the more severe the associated thermal effects.

In this context, this paper describes the implementation of a novel lightning detection network in Brazil, with the goal of generating comprehensive statistical characterizations of key parameters related to the CC. The network employs unique sensors capable of recording lightning electric fields across a wide frequency range, which includes the CC components.

The sensor installation was completed during the final months of the 2023-2024 thunderstorm season, and the preliminary data obtained are discussed throughout this work. Section 2 provides a brief characterization of the network and the technical specifications of the sensors. Section 3 presents preliminary results, including typical waveforms of cloud-to-ground lightning events and a simple statistical analysis on the duration of the measured CCs. The final considerations on the current stage of the project are discussed in Section 4.

II. INSTRUMENTATION

The installation sites of the lightning detection network sensors are indicated on the map shown in Figure 1. The first sensor was placed at the Nova Gameleira Campus of the Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais

(CEFET-MG) in Belo Horizonte, Brazil. Another 4 sensors were installed at different campuses of the Federal Institute for Education, Science and Technology of Minas Gerais (IFMG), all situated within the Belo Horizonte metropolitan area, specifically in the municipalities of Ribeirão das Neves, Betim, Sabará, and Ibitaré. The proposed positioning of these 5 sensors considered the availability of safe and easily accessible sites for the installation team, as well as the need to ensure comprehensive coverage of the Belo Horizonte urban region. Finally, a sixth sensor was implemented in the city of Curvelo, located approximately 140 km from Belo Horizonte, to evaluate the impact of increased distance on the detection capabilities of the network.

Fig. 1 The novel detection network installed in Belo Horizonte, Brazil

The measurement stations employ the HRL™ Detector sensor, manufactured by the American company Fire Neural Network (FNN) [27]. It is a lightning electric fields detector that has two different measurement channels, each with a different frequency response (or passband). The ability to record complete waveforms of lightning electric fields in these two distinct channels and immediately transmit them for cloud storage are the main differentiating aspects of the HRL™ Detector.

The detector's first channel, called HF (high frequency), has an integrator circuit with a time constant of 1 ms, which is suitable for recording the fast electric field variations, such as those produced during the impulsive phase of RS. The fast pulses associated with the attachment process are used to determine the lightning strike location on the ground. For this specific determination, the Time Difference of Arrival (TDoA) technique is employed if simultaneous measurements from at least 3 GPS-synchronized stations are available. The second channel (LF - low frequency) has a time constant of approximately 1 s and is responsible for recording the slower electric field variations, such as those typically produced by the continuous components of the lightning current.

Figure 2 illustrates the detectors installed at 3 different locations: (a) the Nova Gameleira campus of CEFET-MG in Belo Horizonte, (b) the IFMG Campus in Sabará, and (c) the

IFMG Campus in Ribeirão das Neves. The electric field sensors of these devices consist of circular and concentric metallic plate-type antennas, which are connected to the integrator circuits of the HF and LF channels. The outputs of these circuits are sampled by digitizers at a rate of 5 MS/s, ensuring sufficient temporal resolution for the analysis of the various processes that can occur during lightning flashes.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2 Sensors installed at (a) CEFET-MG Nova Gameleira, IFMG (b) Sabará and (c) Ribeirão das Neves

In this work, the data obtained from the HF and LF channels are used in a redundant manner. By applying a numerical signal processing technique known as deconvolution [28], which essentially consists of a correction to the measured signal considering the characteristics of the transfer function of the measurement system, the data from both channels are processed jointly to increase the level of reliability of the analyses.

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Since most of the cloud-to-ground lightning are of the negative downward type [6], the discussion of the preliminary results in this text is focused on this specific type of lightning flash. In this context, Figures 3, 4, and 5 present typical electric field profiles measured by the HF and LF channels of the FNN HRL™ Detector exhibiting distinct particular characteristics.

The event whose electric field waveform is presented in Figure 3 corresponds to a flash that had only one stroke. The onset of the pulse in the HF channel indicates approximately the moment when the downward and upward channels connected, initiating the RS process. The instant at which its

peak occurs is usually used in the application of the TDoA technique to locate the point of incidence on the ground. It is important to mention that, in the LF channel, the exponential decay of the electric field level after the rapid variation at 880 ms is attributed to the time constant of the integrator circuit, and not to a positive variation of the electric field.

Fig. 3 Electric field waveform of a negative downward lightning recorded on 01/31/24, at 20:28:26 (UTC), at IFMG Ribeirão das Neves

Figure 4 shows the electric field waveform of a single stroke flash. This record explicitly indicates, as pointed out by the arrows, the occurrence of an approximately constant intensification of the electric field. This continuous and long-lasting increase - of about 400 ms - is attributed to the flow of a LCC through the plasma channel. Considering that, during this time interval, the channel remains connected to the strike point, transferring charge and heat, its destructive potential is very high. It is important to mention that the lightning location systems currently operating in Brazil [29] are not able to report such occurrences.

Fig. 4 Electric field waveform of a negative downward lightning with a LCC recorded on 01/31/24, at 20:16:36 (UTC), at IFMG Ribeirão das Neves

The electric field waveform illustrated in Figure 5 shows an event that is potentially more damaging to grounded structures. The flash consists of 4 strokes, with the last stroke being followed by a long continuous current. The initial breakdown pulses (IBP) were recorded shortly before 950 ms, preceding the development of the lightning channel. Upon connection to a grounded structure, the first return stroke (RS1) was initiated. Approximately 50 ms after RS1, the second return stroke (RS2) occurred. The third return stroke (RS3) was recorded around 1050 ms, and the fourth stroke (RS4) followed about 20 ms later. Finally, a long continuing current component, exceeding 100 ms in duration, was recorded after the impulsive phase of RS4.

Fig. 5 Electric field waveform of a four-strokes negative downward lightning flash with a LCC following the 4th stroke. The event was recorded on 02/04/24, at 17:31:05 (UTC), at IFMG Ribeirão das Neves.

The analysis of the various records obtained during thunderstorms that occurred between January 12 and March 15, 2024, led to the development of a brief statistical study of the duration of LCCs occurring in the coverage area of the detection network. As discussed earlier, this duration is important because it determines the time interval during which the lightning plasma channel remains connected to the point of incidence.

The results obtained from this study are illustrated in Figures 6a (histogram), 6b (probability density function, PDF) and 6c (cumulative distribution function, CDF). The preliminary analysis of Figure 6 indicates that the lognormal probability density function fits the duration data consistently, following a natural trend for lightning current intensity parameters [30]. The parameters of the obtained approximation are: mean of 92.6128 ms, variance of 3617.12 (ms)², $\mu = 4.3525$ and $\sigma = 0.593182$.

Both the reported value for the mean of the adjusted distribution and the values indicated in the histogram for the arithmetic and geometric means agree with the few data reported in the literature [1,6,7,23–25]. It is interesting to note

that, as expected, the geometric mean of 78 ms is exactly equal to the median value provided by the CDF in Figure 6c, which corresponds to an accumulated probability of 50%.

Fig. 6 Preliminary statistics of the data obtained over two months of CC measurements: (a) histogram, (b) PDF and (c) CDF.

IV. FINAL REMARKS

Although the database constituted in this preliminary analysis of results refers to an observation period of only 63 days, which the authors consider as an embryonic study, it is possible to state that the installed network has great potential to contribute to the provision of results capable of improving knowledge about lightning protection engineering parameters, especially those related to CCs. In this perspective, through the maintenance and constant monitoring of the detectors, the authors of this work intend to obtain a more extensive data set in the next thunderstorm seasons, in order to enable the extension of the statistical study to other event parameters, such as the analysis of the percentage of positive lightning that occur in the region, as well as the multiplicity (number of strokes) of all types of events. Moreover, the network can also provide the locations of the lightning strike points, enabling localized verification of the effects caused by each detected LCC. These long continuing currents are more prone to causing thermal damage.

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